

Recommendation 15:

Using 'Digitalization' to meet the public sector need 'Increase resource productivity'

Status quo:

Digital transformation promises great things for the public sector and the citizens it serves, from lower costs and greater efficiency to real-time services, seamless communication and enhanced program effectiveness. Shared services, greater collaboration and integration, improved fraud management and productivity enhancements enable system-wide efficiencies.

Recommended actions:

Technical challenges:

- An increasingly mobile workforce can expose government networks to additional vulnerabilities
- Legacy IT systems can be risky to replace with new ones but public sector must upgrade, connect and consolidate its infrastructure before it becomes obsolete and unable to support digital and collaborative environments

Non-technical challenges:

- *Training:* The complexity of large-scale digital projects requires specialized skills and expertise, as well as a strong central leadership
- *Security:* It's critical to make online security simple for citizens while maintaining strong protections for their private data.
- *Processes:* It is a challenge to maintain strategic continuity even as political administrations change
- *Organization:* Silos, fragmentation, and the absence of a central owner for nationwide IT infrastructure and common components make it difficult to invest at scale and generate sufficient economies.
- *Ethical issues:* Digital divide in the citizenry

Increase resource productivity:

Frugally utilise available resources (to do more with less) and manage their movement across the public sector in an efficient manner (especially in this era of constrained resources). The sub needs under this header include: fairer distribution of resources, lack of resources, working without budgets, secondment of resources across departments. Our informants expressed their voices as, "Ensure the appropriate resources for the services offered", "Ensure sustainability of the actions and projects undertaken" and "Resources should be sufficient and transferable across departments"

Digitalization:

*Digitalization corresponds the process of the technologically-induced change, whereas digital transformation is described as the total and overall societal effect of digitalization. In a narrower sense, digitalization as well as digital transformation may refer to the concept of "going paperless". **

* Gartner IT Glossary – Digitalization, <http://www.gartner.com/it-glossary/digitalization/>
Wikipedia – Digital transformation, https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_transformation